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**How to foster a High-Tech entrepreneurial mind-set –
A multidisciplinary engineering course for Bachelor students**

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ABSTRACT

It is becoming clearer that the era of digitalisation is reshaping many of the circumstances in world today in a high pace. In order to prepare the graduates in engineering for a future in a labour market which is hard to predict the content and the core competences engineering students develop during their education need to be reconsidered to meet new requests. Today there is a growing interest to develop entrepreneurial competences among students. This paper describes the Bachelor of Science in engineering course “High-Tech Entrepreneurship” developed within an external funded project at the Technical University of Denmark, Copenhagen. The course aims to foster an entrepreneurial mind-set among the students and a deeper understanding of high-technological start-ups. It’s a 5 ECTS course which is open to students from all engineering programmes. In order to measure the students’ progression towards an entrepreneurial mind-set the questionnaire “Entrepreneurial Mind-Set Assessment” is used. The questionnaire consists of 28 statement and the students rate themselves in the beginning of the course and in the end of the course. The results from two cohorts of students, indicates that the course design fulfil its purpose to enhance an entrepreneurial mind-set among the students.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum development, Skills and Engineering Education, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: Entrepreneurial minds-set, multidisciplinary teams, preparing professionals

INTRODUCTION

Engineering Education needs to provide students with a broad mind-set including both a solid foundation of disciplinary knowledge as well as a set of general skills in order to prepare them for their future professional working life as engineers [1]. Here, they will be increasingly met with demands toward atomisation, as well as needs for new technological and sustainable solutions, in terms of not only effective technology but also environmental issues and human development and welfare. In order to prepare the students to be more flexible on the labour market, innovation and entrepreneurship is regarded as some of the new key competences among academics. One example is the work of World Economic Forum which indicates that the fourth industrial revolution will create new conditions for labour in a near future [2]. Graduates from university must in the future to a higher extent be able to take initiative in co-creating work opportunities for themselves and for others, and this in cooperation with colleagues, maybe from other disciplines. They need to learn entrepreneurship in the broader sense which includes an idea and opportunity seeking mindset [3]. At the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), there is a growing awareness about this societal development. In parallel with this, a more systematic approach evolves about the importance of develop a set of general competences among the students that will be necessary for them in order to be well prepared for their future as professional engineers. Competences like learn to learn, information literacy, ethics, design thinking, and entrepreneurship, slowly but steady find its way into the curriculum of the education programmes at DTU. In addition, the physical learning environment are under reconstruction to meet a new way of teaching characterised of digitalised methods, active learning and innovation. The start of DTU Skylab, a student hub for innovation, contributed to enhance the student

activities at DTU towards innovation and entrepreneurship. Due to the establishment of DTU Skylab a concrete place exists where students can work on develop their own ideas, building prototypes in professional workshops and gain support if they want to take their ideas further and start their own business. In 2016, DTU Skylab estimated 44 student start-ups. Through different activities for educators at DTU, they get the opportunity to be brought in contact with DTU Skylab. Some educators get inspiration to make the transition from auditory to laboratory in their way of teach. Within an external project funded by The Danish Industry-Foundation [4] and by the lead of DTU Skylab the course “High-Tech Innovation” was developed. The project aimed to promote a growth mind-set among DTU students. The course described in this paper was the work-package 2 in the project. The course was developed in cooperation between different departments at DTU involving educators and relevant staff members from DTU administration.

1 TRAINING BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN ENGINEERING STUDENTS IN “HIGH-TECH INNOVATION”

The course “High-Tech Innovation” has a novel design in order to foster an entrepreneurial mind-set among the students, paired with a deeper understanding for the processes involved in high-technological start-ups, which often demand involvement and collaboration. It’s a 5 ECTS course which spans over a three-week full time study period and is open to students from all education programmes, giving a multidisciplinary engineering approach.

1.1 Overall aims and central elements in the course

The aims of the course have a much wider perspective than inspire students to start their own businesses. The students should also be able to create own technological ideas during the course and understand the prerequisites for grow of high technological ideas into products or solutions. The students learn about the mechanisms underlying growth and upscaling.

A very important underlying idea in the course is to bring metacognitive knowledge to students about what it means to be an entrepreneurial person and how to use an entrepreneurial mind-set in a wider sense. Metacognitive knowledge refers to knowledge about general strategies, in which tasks and when and how to use them, their effectiveness and also to know oneself and develop a greater awareness of personal strengths and weaknesses [5]. In this case the metacognitive level includes preparing the students for what can be waiting when they as engineers wish to promote development and idea generation in a technological content.

Central elements in the course are i) self-efficacy in a multidisciplinary undertaking ii) capture the bachelor students’ spark to become engineers with the ability for idea generation and creative solutions; and iii) prerequisites for innovation and business growth in a high-technological context. According to the work of Bandura the most central for people to be able to develop, learn and fulfil their potential is their own believes about their capabilities to have control over own actions and the circumstance that effects their lives [6]. That’s the reason why self-efficacy is a central element in this course and the overall aim in the work with the students following “High-tech Entrepreneurship”. Self-efficacy can be supposed to play a central role to unleash entrepreneurial potential [7]. Another study has showed that specifically formal learning in courses and learning from successful role-models are factors that enhance entrepreneurial self-efficacy [8].

1.2 Course Design

The key teaching methods in the course are meetings between experienced high-technological entrepreneurs and the bachelor students in sessions with a narrative approach to teaching [9] and the students' own high-tech idea generation and idea growth process. The narrative teaching approach is overall method in the course. It is not 'just' the experienced entrepreneurs that deliver narratives but the students also develop their ideas by a succession of narratives in the format of continuous pitches as a method for formative assessment. The intension is that this forms a basis from which the students can develop entrepreneurial self-efficacy [8].

The students' learning process in this course is designed following the "Double Diamond" design-model [10]. The model is building on the four phases i) discover (divergent process), ii) define (convergent process), iii) develop (divergent process) and iv) deliver (convergent process), with the divergent and convergent phases comprising of explorative and synthesis work, respectively. The model is introduced to the students in the very beginning of the course and play the role as a guideline through a very open-ended learning process where the students themselves are in charge of their learning. Active learning teaching methods and students working independently are two corner stones in teaching for innovation and entrepreneurship [11].

This first iteration in the Double Diamond is worked through during the first two days in the course during which the students generate individual ideas, form their teams around those ideas and decide what ideas to continue with for the rest of the course. Hence, after this process the students have defined an idea to work on during the rest of the course. After this process, a new divergent period follows where the student teams develop their ideas, and formulate suggestion to how the processes and products they came up with can be grown and up-scaled. The students continually work with a "Realisation Plan" during the course. This tool is important for the progression in the course and helps the students keep on track and enter the last convergent phase in order to produce a concrete solution. Throughout this work by the students they apply the input they receive by the narratives from the high-tech entrepreneurs participating as guest speakers. The students mirror themselves and their own work in the guest speakers and in their entrepreneurial stories. Gradually during the course the students start to act with more and more confidence and show a more professional behaviour in their entrepreneurial work.

During the first course day the students learn how to pitch. Student pitches is an important learning tool in the course and it also has the role as formative assessment. Every Friday the students pitch their work with growing and develop their ideas and receive feedback.

The last convergent phase starts during the last days of the course when the students prepare the finalisation of their "Realisation Plan" for their ideas. The students hand in their work for peer-review by another team. After the process of peer-review the "Realisation Plans" for each team will be handed in for the final assessment. In the summative assessment, the students present their solution during a final pitch at the last day in the course. The course is a non-grading course and the students can pass or fail.

1.3 Use of Intellectual Property Rights

“Intellectual Property Rights” (IPR) is used in “High-tech Innovation” to create an effective driving force for the students’ idea growing process. One of the foundations in the course is to show the students the framework for High Technological innovation. It’s very central in the course that the disciplinary technological knowledge is actively used and in focus. During the third course day after the students have formulated their own technological idea, the students get an introduction to IPR and relevant databases. A read thread in the course is that the students continually have to check if components they need or technical solutions they consider to come further in their idea-grow process already have a patent. IPR used in this way has shown to be an effective method for the students to learn about IPR but also as a method for them to develop their ideas further as well as their technological knowledge.

2 MEHTOD FOR INVESTIGATE DEVLOPMENT OF ENTREPRENUERIAL MIND-SET

The main purpose with the external funded project that made the development of this course possible was to develop initiatives at DTU that provide engineering students at with possibilities to learn about innovation and entrepreneurship in a technological context. There are many small start-ups in Denmark and the challenge is to create start-ups with grow potential that can generate workplaces and have a positive impact for the employment in society. For that reason this project also had a special focus on creating a grow mind-set among engineers students and graduates. Generally, engineers are seen as key actors in order to find new solutions to global challenges and to create more job-opportunities through new products and solutions that can be commercialised. Those circumstances also have an impact on how to design engineering education [12]. The task for work-package 2 in the project was to develop a course for bachelor students which resulted in the course described in this paper. The project was aiming for a prof-off concept and we needed to find a way to investigate how well the course fulfilled it purposes to promote knowledge about and a mind-set towards high technological innovation, growth and entrepreneurship among the bachelor students following the course.

2.1 Investigation design and evaluations of the course

During the project period the course was held as a pilot try-out three times. In the 3-week study period in January 2017 the course was established as an ordinary electable course for bachelor students from all study lines at DTU. In order to learn how the course designed work, and if the learning and assessment activities chosen were suitable for the course aims several evaluations were conducted during the piloting phase. In the first course pilot August 2015 only six students participated in the course. The course was evaluated by a focus group interview directly after the final assessment. In the second pilot in January 2016 there were 32 students participating. Also this time a focus group was conducted with a representative from each student team. The third time the course was to be piloted in August 2016 it was cancelled due to too few participants. The first time the course was held after the project period in January 2017, there where again many students in the course, 33 participants. This time no focus group interview was held, but the ordinary course evaluation for all courses at DTU was done. In all those qualitative evaluations the students have reported that the course fulfils its purpose with regards to the course design and the learning process established in the course.

2.2 Student survey

The survey "Entrepreneurial Mindset Self-Assessment" was used in the second pilot of the course and the first time the course was held as an ordinary course in order to investigate deeper how well the course meets its objectives with respect to development of an entrepreneurial mind-set among the students. In the survey the students rate themselves on 28 statements on a Likert scale 1 – 5 about traits central in an entrepreneurial mind-set [13]. The students in "High-Tech Innovation" rate themselves in the very beginning of the course, pre-test, and in the very end of the course right after the final assessment, post-test.

3 RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

In this section the result of the survey and a statistical analyses are presented. The pre-test is referred to as pre16 or 17 and the post-test is referred to as post 16 or 17.

3.1 Data from student learning outcome

Data are collected from two years - 2016 and 2017 - where we have asked the students to fill out the questionnaire before and after attending the course (pre and post). This gives us 4 batches of answers named pre16, post16, pre17 and post17. Data consists of 32 observations from pre16, 33 observations from post16, 24 observations from pre17, and 26 observations from post17. For all questions the answers were given on a 5 point Likert scale where 1 indicates "Strongly disagree" and 5 indicates "Strongly agree". For pre17 we found 5 cases where the cross was placed in between to possibilities on the scale. In these cases the lowest number was used. We found one question with no answer indicated. Here the answer was coded as 3. For post17 we found 7 cases where the cross was placed in between to possibilities on the scale. In these cases the lowest number was used. 1 questionnaire had only answers on the first page (the first 7 questions). This questionnaire was not included in the analysis. 3 questionnaires had 5 as an answer for all questions. These were kept in the analysis. The data were collected on paper to ensure that the answers were given in an anonymous way. This means that we do not have paired observations (we do not know which pre and post questionnaires come from the same student). Having had that information would have made us able to make a more powerful statistical analysis and it is worthwhile to consider whether it will be possible to get that information in future studies. As a part of filling out the questionnaire the students are asked to state their study direction. Unfortunately, this was not done by many of the students so we have not been able to use this information in our analysis. Future studies will focus on getting this information right as it will be interesting to see if there are differences between different study directions or groups of study directions.

3.2 Statistical analysis

The mean scores show a tendency that the scores after having attended the course are higher than before attending the course. The 28 questions in the questionnaire are grouped into four groups concerning "Problem solving and critical thinking" (8 questions), "Teamwork" (7 questions), "Business acumen" (8 questions) and "Societal issues" (5 questions) - here called the P, T, B and S group.

We have fitted a linear model to the average response for each of the four groups with two explanatory variables and their interaction. The first explanatory variable indicated whether it was a pre or a post score, and the second one whether the score was from 2016 or 2017. The last explanatory variable is the interaction between the two main factors. The interaction gives the possibility of having different pre-post effects for the two years. For all four groups we found that the interaction was not significant (p-values between 0.06 and 0.39). Moreover the effect of year was not

significant (p-values between 0.11 and 0.77). For all four groups we found a significant difference between the scores before taking the course and after (p-values < 0.005). The strongest effect was seen in the group S where it was estimated to be 2.1. For the rest of the groups it was estimated to 0.61 (P), 0.69 (T) and 0.66 (B). We also checked the assumptions (e.g. normally distributed residuals) which was OK. We also tried out the corresponding models for the individual questions in the questionnaire instead of the average of the four groups. These analysis showed the same tendencies but because of the mass significance problem (when you make many statistical tests in average 5% of them will show significance by chance) we stick to the results concerning the groups. A visual presentation of the results for all the questions is shown in fig. 1. The figure shows the mean results for all the questions (for both years as the analysis did not see a difference between years) for pre and for post.

Fig. 1: A visual presentation of the results for all the questions. The figure shows the mean results for all the questions (for both years as the analysis did not see a difference between years) for pre and for post.

4 SUMMARY

The results show that the students move in a positive direction in the all groups of questions and the conclusion is that they learn from the process in the course. What is interesting is the difference in pre- and post for Business Acumen is not as big as for the societal issues. We expected a bigger difference regarding Business Acumen because we do not consider that a core topic in undergraduate course. The results shows that Problem Solving and Team Work are rated quite equal by the students which indicates that the students independent on engineering programme are quite used to work in that way. The biggest difference in the students' rating is on Societal Issues. Reasons for this can be that the students during the course see the relevance of the multidisciplinary aspect in socially relevant problems, not only through their own discipline but from the multidisciplinary engineering undertaking. That is probably something new for many engineering undergraduate students and an important

experience in order to understand how, and become motivating for doing a difference through innovation in a high technological context.

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